

Reading ‘Colonial’ and ‘Post-Colonial’ Methodologies on Land: Perspectives from the Hill Tribes of Manipur

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The historical experience of hill tribes¹ in ‘post-colonial’ Manipur in relation to state laws and policies, administration and development process around the question of land has invariably been the subject of much controversy over the decades. One such continuum is the recent contention between the hill tribals and state government – aided by valley settlers over land area identified in the construction of National Sports University (NSU) in the foothill of Manipur. In these lights the paper set forth that, such continuity illustrates the intactness of colonial knowledge and power: predominantly of caste & western epistemological framework perpetuated in the existing state structures, coaxed with ethnic power relations (majoritarianism). In doing so, the author revisits the historical trajectories of colonial encounter; the basis of colonial epistemology, methodological issues that it manifests in post-colonial structures.

Keywords: Land, Tribes, Indigenous people, Colonial, Post-colonial, State

Introduction

Manipur is one ‘post-colonial’ Indian state in the North-east region, born out of the historical encounter of British colonialism and later India’s (‘post-colonial’) nation-state processes. Ethnically, the state is inhabited by three major ethnic groups; the Meiteis, the Nagas and the Kukis. The dominant group i.e., Meiteis are historically identified more into characters of Hindu-caste society due to their aged-old association with Hinduism, whereas the Nagas and kukis are categorised as tribes, and subalternised by the civilising-proselytising mission of the colonial rule. The Meiteis account 59.82 per cent of total state population and inhabited the valley while the tribals (Nagas and Kukis) constitute 40.18 per cent of the populations and inhabited in the hills (Census of India, 2011). In land ownership system, Manipur can be broadly classified into hills and valley. Land in the valley is pre-dominantly under the regime

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of individual and state ownership. Whereas in the hills, community land ownership still holds a paramount place, governed by their own respective customary laws and institutions.

The historical experience of tribes in ‘post-colonial’ Manipur in relation to state laws, policies, administration, and development process around the question of land has invariably been the subject of much controversy over the decades. One such continuum is the recent contention between the tribal hill dwellers and state government – aided by valley dwellers over the land area for constructing National Sports University (NSU) in the foothill areas of Manipur. In this light, the paper argues that, in a larger structural contour these unequivocally speaks the intactness of colonial knowledge and power – predominantly of hindu-caste and western epistemological framework perpetuated in the existing state structures coaxed with ethnic power relations (majoritarianism). This requires revisiting of historical trajectories of colonial encounter; the basis of colonial epistemology, methodological issues that informed state making, its convergence in the communal power relation and the entanglement of colonial knowledge and agencies in the ‘post-colonial’ era. At these backdrop, situating the context (of the paper) historically being woven through the colonially constitutive discourse; the author employs Foucauldian framework of ‘historical investigation’ to unravel the continuity and discontinuity of past and present in the subject of power - knowledge discourse, and calls ‘contemporary’² appraisal that emphasises ‘history as an important subject in understanding the present and reclaiming history as a critical and essential aspect of decolonization’ (Smith, 1999: 29-30).

Laying out the Colonial Methodological Problems

Within the colonial knowledge enterprise, the inception of western genealogical understanding on land first originates from the ideas of John Locke (1690) – conceptualise land as properties, that it belongs to nobody premised as ‘state of nature’. His ideas share a close intellectual affinity with the traditions of Christian cosmological worldview that sets its belief that human beings possess divine supernatural origin superior to other living organisms (forest, animals, plants, trees etc.). And therefore, it affirms that humans are assigned by God to govern and administer nature for the well-being of human society. In this Cosmology, the duality of Human vs Nature / ‘Nature and Culture’ appears indisputably interlinked as the nature of relationship, placing human as the centre of Christian cosmology (Palson & Descola, 2013: 2 - 9). The better man utilises and civilise nature, the greater it fulfils the virtue of his existence on earth. In the scientific domain they called it as ‘environmental orientalism’ whereby science – ‘baconian science’ and ‘mathematical equation’ to the natural world, is given utmost privilege from the enlightenment period. Within this tradition, it later gave birth to the philosophy of utilitarianism; dubbed economic well-being as the ultimate underlying essence of nature. In the later centuries of global industrial economy and capitalism, the concept of ‘environmental paternalism’ got introduced and push forth within the dominant chain of western science, characterised by relations of protection in post industrialisation. This involves privileging scientific expertise

and establishing a moral ground that humans have a responsibility not only to fellow human beings but also to fellow inhabitants of this entire natural ecosystem (Palson, 1996a; Sivaramakrishnan, 1995: 6).

Lockean optimistic notion of human 'state of nature' to a remarkable extent laid a foundation unfurling to the emergence of 'liberal self' which later mutates to composite elements of 'capitalism'; imminently facilitated by instrumental temperament of science and modernity of the enlightenment period. Over the centuries throughout the colonial history, the advancement of science was instrumentally used for the imperial expansion since the early centuries (mainly during 17th and 18th) which Jacob and Steward (2004) shrewdly remark - it benefits only those who possessed it. In critics of capitalism, Marx (1867) analysed these modes of development as the capitalist mode of control and production through the process of '*Primitive accumulation*' where people and communities are dispossessed of their land and labour. The continuity witnesses the nexus of state and capitalism under the banner of science, modernity and development fused conceivably well in the affairs of liberal democracy. Das (1996: 27-57) theorised the nature of these states, as the 'capital determination of the state' or 'capitalist centric state' of affairs governmentalised by the capitalist regime – neo-liberal regime. In these lights, Garrett Hardin's work (1968) - "tragedy of the commons" – a Malthusian account is one colonial piece that advocates on the rationality of individual ownership of resources under the watch of government and technological advancement. His thesis was written in context of western industrial society (particularly of rural countryside) responding to an unrestrained population growth and capitalist tendency-hoarding of resources by few in the given area of shared commons. Later, his theory enjoys recognition within the colonial universalising project and later it was taken up by the "gathering forces of neo-liberal reaction in the 1990s which became the 'scientific' foundation of world bank and International Monetary Fund (IMF), viz. enclosure of common and privatization of public property...the message is clear: we must never treat the earth as the 'common treasury'. We must be ruthless and greedy." (Boal, 2007; cited in Angus, 2017). His work became one among the most suppressive imperial theory that haunts indigenous communities across the globe who relies on sustenance of shared commons.

Discerning the idea of modern state in relation to land and property in colonial and post-colonial discourse, Lockean conception of state predominantly laid an overarching foundation. His thought remains magnanimously instrumental in the constitution of colonial state - and the making of the modern idea of state; fundamentally derived from the thesis of individual rights/liberty and state as the administrator/governor of individual citizens. Sivaramakrishnan (1995a) notes, the British laws and policies in the 19th century was hugely driven by utilitarianism, and classical economics to a large extent. Based on these embedded ideas, private ideology – ownership of any form was considered superior than communal relations. It is one such popularising ideal, India roots its foundation in her state making; hobnobbing with the economics of utilitarianism – that premised and claims her vast land and forest areas as economic resources in purview of the state. The power legitimisation

of 'imminent domain' exercised by the colonial state through 'taxonomising' and 'categorising' land, forest and resources based on capitalistic utility became even more menacing in the 'post-colonial' India. 'Nehruvian model' of development with heavy investment on mega industries and infrastructural development projects called as 'Temple of modern India' is one such example of colonial legacy in the post-independent period. Likewise in north-east India, land takes the form of economic resources, security, governance and recently tourism imprisoning the varied cultural values and meanings (Fernandes, 2017; Bodhi & Ziipao, 2019; Upadhyay, 2017). In post 1990s neo-liberal forces of liberalisation and privatisation emerged undisputedly powerful through the national policies and development discourse that legitimises the private ownership, 3rd party transfer of land, unrecognising community ownership, arbitrarily devised and coordinated under the principle of 'eminent domain' from nation-state. The repressive weapon of the state; right of the government to acquisition of any area of land (of national importance) within its territory is the colonial legacy coalesced with the Indian feudal-caste society. At these exogenously compounding methodological backdrop through state and neo-liberal forces, indigenous tribal's lived realities rooted in reciprocity with land and forest under community relationship became vulnerably caught at receiving end.

The central methodological problem, epistemologically the most suppressive perhaps derived from the colonial notion of 'other' and the 'new world' – dubbed indigenous people and their worldviews as the untamed "state of nature". Hobbes explicit remark "savage people in many places of America" is the blatant justification of the state of nature (1985[1651]:187). Therefore, land of the natives/indigenous people was viewed as '*vacuum domicilium*' which means 'no man's land'. Socio-cultural and political system of the natives that exist in '*difference was interpreted as absence*'. Epistemic imperial superiorisation over indigenous people/natives through 'evolutionary' touchstone essentialising indigenous people as 'primitive', 'uncivilised', 'barbaric', 'animal kingdom', 'people without history' served as the basis of various colonial exploitation, injustice, and genocides. Against these colonial constructions about 'other' and indigenous people, Souza (2016) boldly called out as an act of epistemic violence – 'epistemicide'/'cognitive injustice' While refuting the colonial anthropological discipline, Fabian (1983) calls the arrogant fable's out as 'denial of coevalness' perceived and written about (accessed) 'others' through temporal time and space objectively external to European notion of time. This monochronic colonial notion of time and knowledge about 'other' was intellectually instrumentalised through several disciplines; constructed, built, and further induced the expansion of the colonial regime. The philosophical temper of this methodological manifestation was further justified and devised through several international laws, legal regime, state institutions and governance system, with moral institution – religion (Christianity). The enlightenment period; growth of science and industrial revolution greatly advances this colonial doctrine. The widespread enlightenment heirs of this powerful intellectual regime of science and positivist tradition produced varied forms of institutions; intellectual tradition via methodological realm. Edward Said (1978) refers to this process as a Western discourse about the 'other' which is supported by 'institutions, vocabulary, scholarship, imagery, doctrines, even colonial bureaucracies

and colonial styles' (Said, 1978: 2).

In these systemic colonial epistemological layouts and its diffusion across region and colonies, tribes in India experience systemic colonial assault. The colonial notion of 'others' - 'primitive', 'savage', 'uncivilised', 'barbaric' etc. got introduced into objectified terms as 'criminal tribe', 'forest tribe', 'primitiveness', 'backwardness' which were exogenously named and classified in the lowest rank of the civilisational order (Beteille, 1989). Later, along the colonial myth of categorising and civilising tribes, the dominant hindu caste societies also propagated the linear colonial framework of conceptualising tribal societies appropriating them as 'backward caste', 'backward Hindus', that epistemologically postulate a theory to integrate tribes into caste societies (N.K Bose 1975; Ghurye, 1893). However, Xaxa (2008) argued that there's a sense of continuity of identifying tribes outside the civilisation from pre-colonial Hindu civilisational conception of tribes to colonial construction, and subsequently the post-colonial understanding of tribes. In this system of knowledge, caste became the mirror to understand tribal society, and proposes a theory of 'tribe-caste-class continuum' and thus for the tribes to progress and develop they have to integrate into caste societies. In the words of Ghurye, the population of tribes were broadly categorised into two; tribes of central India and tribes of north-east India – and proposes to make them integrated into Hindu nation through Hinduisation (for tribes of central India) and to politically incorporated through strong administrative apparatus (for tribes of north east).³ Having these complex assembling of domineering epistemologies, the agency of the indigenous communities or tribes and their epistemic vulnerability gets subsumed and fragmented; that ultimately leads to expansion of several colonial-paternal institutions, laws and policies on land, forest and resources, environmental laws, industrial laws, and policies which remain suppressively insensitive and exploitative to indigenous people even in the post-colonial era.

The colonial encounter and the making of state: Historical-Political Context

It was the '*Treaty of Yandabo*' that made British Raj annexed the geographically isolated terrain, 'contiguously an unadministered territory', populated by diverse ethnic communities in the north western part of Burma and north eastern part of British India in 1826. The region was then known as 'North – East frontier' during the colonial period, and later as 'North-east' region in the post-colonial era. With the Treaty of Yandabo between the British India and Burmese Government, upper Assam was annexed in 1838, and subsequently it extended to Cachar hills, Khasi hills, Jaintia hills, Garo hills, Naga hills, Manipur, Lushai hills in 1892. Before the colonial rule, hill people were what Scott calls 'self governed' people, whereas valleys were mostly under the rule of kingdoms. The British, due to constant raids and resistances meted out to their expeditions in the hilly areas, and indirectly administer the region under 'non-interference policy' and later categorised it as – 'Backward tracts' in 1919, 'Excluded areas' and 'Partially excluded areas' in 1935. This series of isolationist-colonies firendly model of rule was developed. In karlsson's (2011) account, the 'invention of tribes' as synonymous to 'backwardness', 'remoteness' 'warlike' etc. derived from colonial mercantile interest in administering the plain areas richly endowed by fertile land, which was previously owned and mutually accessed by the

valley dwellers and the tribesman as the hills were mostly 'barren'. Seeing the commercial viability, the British administratively pushed and alienate away the tribesman into the hills - upper assam. In the process, it demarcates "hills and valley, nomadic and sedentary, tribal areas from 'proper assam' and seen hill settlers outside the historical pace of development and progress" (Karlson 2011; 270); classified in the evolutionary touchstone that relegates hill dwellers into periphery, and inferior to the alternative civilisation presented by the high caste of the 'mainland'/valley kingdoms that inhabits with them for centuries (Khapai, 2020; 151). To substantiate these line of argument, Chakraverty's (1989) account also serves a significant linkage. He writes: "During king Pratap Singh of Ahoms (1606-1641 AD), the system of 'Posa' was introduced regarding the hill tribes of East frontier". This system regulates the needs and demands of hill countries from the harvest that was produced from the fertile 'duar' areas in the valley. Several 'duar' intersects this belt of land through which hill people-maintained contact with the plains. In return of these privileges by the hill tribes, they had to recognise the lordship of the Ahom king and pay annual tribute to him with their annual products(Chakraverty 1989: 408).

While in Manipur, the contact with the colonial rule although subdued the people on one hand it further re-enforces the already existing Hindu-caste notion on tribes i.e., non-Hindu hill dwellers as backward Hindus/out of Varna System, and peripheralise the hill dwellers further from historical time and development. Several historical accounts record the existence of congenial relationship between the hill dwellers/tribals and valley dwellers/Meiteis in the form of trade, barter system, occasional raids, etc. in the early pre-Hinduism era. With the adoption of Hinduism as the state religion by king Garibniwaz in late 17th and early 18th century, stringent measures were introduced and imposed in the form of *Lallup*⁴ system (Kamei, 2004). This resulted to shattering of relationship between the hills and valley. By 1762, the arrival of East India company and its signing of friendly alliance with Maharaja Bhagya Chandra in 1762, the expedition of Meitei monarch in hill areas became more intensified with heavy military expedition. However, later Meitei monarch was annexed by the colonial rule, which led to introduction of dual administration; hills under Manipur state Darbar and valley areas under Meitei Maharaja. Similarly, under British rule repressive policy was introduced in the form of 'taxation' and reimposition of *Lallup*⁵ system in the hills which led to several revolts from the hills; Kuki uprising (1917-19), Zeliangrong revolt led by H. Jadonang & Rani Gaidinliu (1927-33) (Ziipao, 2020: 77). Thus, one can observe that the experience of tribes in Manipur today in post India's independence or so called 'post-colonial' in Manipur is marked by blended version of the two domineering epistemologies - manifested in several state laws, policies and institutions provided for the hills today.

With the British mercantilism policy in the fertile valleys, and the resistant 'war-like tribals' in the wild hill terrain, the colonial rulers treated hill areas and plain areas differently in the 'frontier region' as discussed above. The introduction of Assam Land and Revenue Regulation (AL&RR) 1886 in one such policy, which later got extended to Imphal valley of Manipur until 1960 (now replaced by MLR&R Act 1960). And the hills were administered under 'Backward tract' (1919), 'Excluded

areas' and 'Partially excluded' areas. By post-independence period, the concept 'Scheduled Tribe' was signed up as a politico-administrative category, and notified with new entries in the existing lists (Bhuria Report Vol. 1, 2002 as cited in Leo 2018) where several communities from the region were listed as 'Scheduled tribe' from the region.

Throughout the colonial period, several records of raids, resistance against the colonial power were recorded in the history. The British consolidation of the region through various colonial tools - administration, classification, ethnographic accounts, cartographies, etc. served the project of state making and left the region in the state of ethnic discontent and political perplexities thereafter. Similar newer political demands and resistance movement continued in India's post-independence period, perhaps it got surfaced even more complex with several ethno-national political claims and counter claims deeply rooted in the colonial making of state. Responding to the heterogeneous political outcries of the region, 'post-colonial' / 'neo-colonial' India employs the similar colonial tactics - administrative schemes to ambiguously accommodate the various 'ethno-national' movements and aspiration of the region, that results to re-organisation of state in 1960s and 1970s. The colonial policy and the ideological continuity in post-colonial india illuminates the works of Bernard Cohn (1996: 1-2), of how modalities in politico-administrative terms was created to serve people's interest and their role within the system to fulfil the project of state making through 'officialising' the systems and procedures. Nevertheless, the reorganisation of states and the other constitutional provisions like 6th Schedule, Article 371(A) and 371(C) although accommodate several political discontentment to some extent, it resulted in the emergence of varied political backlash, claims and counterclaims along ethnic lines, minority versus majority, hills-valley and stirs up several identity politics in the region. Because, in both colonial and post-colonial administrative apparatus – drawing state boundary, the existing socio-cultural and political boundaries and sensitivities of different ethnic communities were disbanded and inject 'divide and rule policy'. Thus, to simply conceive these riddles, although the British colonial rule left India in 1947, much of colonial laws and institution remain intact with the post-colonial India's state making. As argued by scholars from the region, it is merely a transfer of power. Tribes in the hills still faces an indifferent treatment by the dominant societies allying with the making of state.

It is in this historical context the idea of Manipur as a princely state (in 1891) and the birth of Manipur as a state entity (in 1972) under the Indian constitution came into being. The creation of Manipur as a state was never (or barely) a political will of the different ethnic communities (Nagas, Kukis and others) living in Manipur today. And therefore, Manipur became politically and ethnically a volatile state ever since, the signing of merger agreement in 1949, and aftermath the political fallout that deeply divide between hills and valley and across ethnic lines. On this account U.A Shimray (2013) writes:

The Naga National League (NNL) headed by Athiko Daiho, in September 1946, was organised to consolidate Nagas of Manipur in order to bring together Naga people separated by colonial boundaries...The Naga league categorically assert that they will not remain in Manipur since the Manipuri Maharaja had never conquered Nagas and declared that it would be impossible for the Nagas to preserve the best of their culture,

tradition, customary laws and political practices. The movement expressed their strong desire to merge with the Nagas Hill district of Assam (now the present Nagaland state) through the boycott of the preparation of the electoral rolls in the Naga areas and the election to the first Legislative Assembly of Manipur in 1948 (Nagaland Journal, 2013).

Similarly, T.S. Gangte (2007) also writes:

The Kukis National Assembly (KNA) submitted a memorandum to then Prime Minister of India Jawaharlal Nehru on 24th March 1960 and demanded for the immediate creation of 'Kuki state' comprising all the Kuki inhabited area of Manipur.

And therefore, the organisation of Manipur state and its making has always been ethnically driven - centered around the political tune of majoritarianism. The inhabitants from the valley that occupy 10 percent of total geographical area represent 40 seats, and the Nagas, Kukis and other unallied tribes⁶ (33 tribes) that inhabit 90 percent of total geographical area with 42.8% of the state population (2011 census) represent only 19 seats based on 1971 census. The call to undo the divide between hills and valley, delimitation exercise was introduced in 2008 and 2020. However, the dominant community - Meiteis has been politically hijacking the move as 'unnatural population growth'. Such that the politics of hills and valley, despite delimitation exercise of 2008 and 2020 (from the Centre) met deliberate denial from the state government with massive supports from valley based political parties and civil bodies. Kamei (2020) calls out as a deliberate 'denial of rights to hill communities'. Leaders and scholars from the hills discerned it as the structural template crafted by the unequal power sharing between hills and the valley. And therefore, the incessant denial upon the implementation of 6th Schedule in the hill areas, non-devolution of legislative and financial power to the existing hill areas autonomous district councils undeniably speaks the edifice of majoritarianism politics in the state. Piang (2019: 54) observed these processes as an 'institutional exclusion to the hill tribes of Manipur'.

Colonial legacy – 'Post-colonial' State on Land: a Methodological Exploitation

At these backdrops of totalising project of the Meiteis with a series of institutional exploitation, indubitably, one of the most controversial state legislations that endangers indigenous hill tribes is the Manipur Land Revenue and Reforms Act, 1960, that dates back to colonial land law called Assam Land and Revenue Regulation (AL&RR) 1886, which subsequently was later imported to Imphal valley post India's independence. The MLR&RA, 1960 was enacted to administer land and its distribution in the valley that excludes hill areas (Section [1] 2 clause). However, in the 6th Amendment Act of 1989 and 1992, devious attempts were made by the state government to remove the section (1) 2 clause 'except the hill areas' in the Act to bring uniformity of land laws in the state. Removal of the clause 'except the hill areas there of' would allow state government to bring *de jure* control over land in the

hills and allow non-tribals to purchase land in the tribal areas. Even more recently in 2015 the state government contentiously passed “three anti-tribal bills” (as popularly known) which one among of them was MLR&LR (Seventh Amendment) to institutionally dispossess land from the tribals. However, these crafty moves from the state was strongly opposed and protested by the tribal bodies. The constant push by the state government for uniform land laws in Manipur on one hand, and the non-extension of 6th Schedule coupled with paternalistic treatment of the existing hill districts councils on the other is widely read by the tribals as a deliberate institutional assault by the state – aided by valley based civil and political groups. In these whole exclusionary process, disproportionate representation in the state assembly between hills and valley kept structurally reflected in hijacking the democratic functioning of the state.

Furthermore, MLR&LR (Sixth Amendment) bill proposed to insert a new section 13(B): “Power to regulate and control Jhum or migratory cultivation, the state government may make rules for regulating Jhum cultivation for protection of environment, catchments areas of irrigation, hydroelectric and water supply project”. This clause procreates contestation with the power given to existing Autonomous District Councils (chapter: 3 [15 & 16]) and customary laws over land and forest in the hill areas. Moreover, the state government, over the years, had begun arbitrarily implementing the Act in the foothill tribal areas. As a result, number of villages from three hill districts; Tamenglong, Senapati, and Churachandpur have faced the loss of land ownership and alienation from their ancestral land (Panmei, 2010). The Act was extended to 29 villages of Churachandpur district, 14 villages in Senapati district, and 14 villages in Khoum Valley of Tamenglong district (Devi 2006; Dena 2009; Roluahpuiah, 2020). Panmei further pointed out the luring component of the Act is that the state government under the gazette notification have power to define “Hill Areas”. It demarcates lands in the hill districts into hilly and low-lying areas. Low-lying land in the hill districts are not counted as hill areas. Moreover, any land dispute arising out of the act is legally authorised to deputy commissioner whose decision is final. Consultation with local people or inhabitants finds no mention in the Act (Panmei 2010a). And therefore, the act directly dismisses the existing customary laws and institutions of the tribal communities. One of the negative implications of the said Amendment is the case of Saikot village of Churachandpur district. The chief and the villagers who enjoyed full rights over land and other forest since the colonial days are now turned into illegal ‘encroachers’ as per Section 14 and 15 of the Act said – “a person in a tribal village can be treated as trespasser or encroacher if he does not apply for allotment of the land which he possessed or occupied for generations without any hitch”. Similar implication is witnessed in the current acquisition of land in the construction of National Sports University (NSU), at Konsakhul foothill areas under erstwhile Senapati district (now Kangpokpi district). Imphal West district revenue department has been manoeuvring a claim that the university site falls under MLR&LR 1960 (Koutruk Dag. No. 1) and thus the claim by the Konsankhul villagers were baseless. For Konsankhul villagers (Thadou and Liangmai Tribe) the land ancestrally belongs to them since time immemorial, and they asserted that there is no ‘Patta land’

in the hills and MLR&LR Act 1960 doesn't apply in tribal hill areas (Haokip, 2020; Kamei, 2015a). In these institutional continuity of negating tribals voice through maintaining and extending land records and formalisation in the hill areas, Kipgen (2018) observed that for tribals of Manipur in post-independent India became more complex and repressive than the colonial regime.

Another indirect attempt that concord with the customary land holding system is the Manipur Land Use Policy 2014, enacted to keep check and regulate the 'unscientific' land use system in hill areas as an environmental measure. The policy was strongly opposed by the tribal bodies and remained unsought in the hill areas. The policy ignorantly overlooked the existing authority of the village council, and introduced 'Village Development Council' (VDC) under the aegis of the state administration. Further VDC was streamlined as a lowest grassroots' body in the administrative hierarchy and exclude village chief or headman in the body. It does either mention any role of tribals in sustainable management of their land and forest resources (Kipgen, 2018). Even the Autonomous District Councils, the people's mandate body in the purview of state in the hills, have no administrative power over the policy. For hill tribals there exist a symbiotic socio-cultural relationship between the village council and land holding system. Conveniently advocating forest conservation and management outside the purview of village chiefs/headman and council is simply a subtle aggression of power by the state.

One of the major contesting domains is the state's claim of ownership in conservation and protection of forest, wildlife and forest products under Manipur Forest Rules 1971 and Wildlife Protection (Manipur) Act 1974.⁷ Under these Acts the state forest department is empowered with executive and judicial power sidelining customary laws and institutions of the tribes. Existing Indian forest laws are colonial heirs of Indian Forest Act 1927 that justifies the crown monopoly over forest and natural resources. Manipur Forest Rules 1971, which is one of the legal handbooks of forest management in the state, is one that traces its ideological and methodological origin to colonial forest laws and seeks to justify 'imminent domain' in the hill areas of Manipur. Forest in the hill areas of Manipur is generally categorised as "unclassed forest"; those which are out of the state purview,⁸ but have arbitrarily declared twenty (20) 'Reserved Forest' in the tribal areas of Manipur (Statistical Handbook of Manipur, 2002). Besides taxes are being collected by the forest department on forest produces like timber, charcoal, sand, stones, and other forest produces under forest beat office check post even in 'unclassed forest' areas and partially regulated the forest management (personal communication with the beat officer, 12th Dec 2019). The state forest department is gradually seizing the paternal control over conservation and protection of 'flora' and 'fauna' in the tribal hill areas irrespective of forest categories. This legal regime of the state was corroborated by the scientific regime of 'environmental paternalism' and undermine the tribal knowledge system in respect to conservation and management of forest and its ecosystem, and side-lined and penalised them. There is brutal insensitivity of the state towards cultural and economic lives of the tribal people whereby their livelihood practice of hunting and gathering of foods from forest (which is still practicing in many interior villages) are called out as illegal, offences and penalising it. In fact, tribal villages have their own culturally

bounded hunting regulatory mechanism with respect to time and season. In 2018, a man from Makan village of Kamjong district (bordering to Myanmar) was arrested by the police with the involvement of cyber police on account of posting the hunted deer in the social media (<https://nagajournal.com/naga-news/youth-arrested-for-circulating-hunted-deer-images-on-social-media/>, 2018). Moreover, in Ukhrul district there are more than 80 legal cases registered against the local tribal people under various state Act viz. the Wildlife (Protection) Act of 1974, and the Forest Conservation Act, 1980 (personal communication with a forest ranger, 5th July, 2019/documents not revealed). The arbitrary attitude of the state and the ultimate legitimacy of the state legal regime over tribals socio-cultural and economic lives and their institutions is an oppressive colonial attitude, perhaps a legal assault to indigenous tribal communities. Conceivably, customary laws and practices cannot remain sacrosanct to contemporary environmental issues and concerns. However, the abject negation to tribals' lived reality and imposition of repressive state laws make the situation even more detrimental.

Undeniably, one of the emerging contestations over tribal land is the repressive state policy that claim the right of ownership over resources, and the acquisition of land for infrastructural development. One such case is Mapithel Dam in Ukhrul district which the project acquired 2,972.28 hectares of land including settlement area, cultivable land and agriculture land. Issues and conflicts related to clause of 'compensation' and 'rehabilitation' remain unresolved till today. Moreover, the extractive state regime with the use of GIS tool continues to identify and survey land in the hills for extraction of mineral resources.³ Some of them have already signed Memorandum of Understanding and had given license to multi-national companies for extraction without the consent of the villagers/land owners. One of such case is the Chromite Mining at Phangrei, Ukhrul, and limestone mining at Hungpung (underway). Interestingly, Section 24A (2) of the MMDRA, 1957, stipulated tribals as the occupiers of surface of the land in the context of social, cultural, religious tradition of significance, the underneath of land belongs to State (Jajo 2017). While on the other hand, the state institutions and mechanism for tribes concerning with protection and governance follows an exclusionary path, denying the rights and justice to hill tribals (Bhatia, 2020). To sum up, the state through different mechanisms and categories: land laws, forest rules and policies, wildlife and environment protection/conservation, mining laws, interwoven through a complex overlapping methods, conceptual generalisation and procedures continue to manoeuvres into the whims and fancies of the state and those in power. In this whole process, tribals were susceptibly cornered at the state of being exploited and marginalised.

Conclusions

With the colonial encounter, structurally, there has been a subtle disintegration in the tribal knowledge system, erosion of customary laws, values and institutions, and more specifically in the land holding system, whereby the making of modern state and its machineries are seen as an external agent informed by certain colonial mode of power and knowledge. For the hill tribes, the state appears to be suppressive either

directly through the imposition of several laws and policies or indirectly through the processes of governance, institutions, development processes in a paternalistic fashion as far as subject on land is concern. Therefore, the positionality of state in context of Manipur deserves an attention of re-reading from the methodological standpoint of ethnic power relation; nature of representation, mode of inclusion and exclusion, socio-cultural sensitivities of difference, historical relationships among communities /hills and valley dynamics and most importantly the subservient inheritance of colonial knowledge and power. It calls to critically revisit the historical trajectories of colonial experience and the embedded body of power and knowledge that informed and coordinated the process of state making. Whilst, acknowledging the need to re-imagine state that embraces plurality and space for dialogic imagination across communities, and to restore the congenial historical relationship between the hill tribes and valley - ‘Ching tam amani’, the dominant group – Meitei/valley dwellers must take cognizance of the unequal power relationships shared between hills and valley, and the historical conditions that shape them into dominant position, and the existing disparities across socio-economic and development parameters. Thus, the relationship between hill tribes and state is not so much of a symbiotic one, but more an assertion of self/tribal agency for epistemological recognition that constantly resists and negotiate in the light of fostering the organicity of tribes and restore the fragmenting ones to flourish a space of dialogue and meaningful co-existence (Akhup, 2015: 2-3).

Besides, there’s an emerging tension of manifesting colonial epistemologies within the tribal society that requires special attention. While encountering with dominant categories like modernity, state processes, development; rampant commoditisation, privatisation and commercialisation of land seem surfacing subserviently within the tribal communities, negating the larger socio-cultural and onto-cosmic components. This in fact is leading to a series of land accumulation in the hands of few, and growing intensity of land dispossession/alienation for economically disadvantaged position in a sophisticated manner (Somingam, 2020: 138). In words of Fernandes (2017) this unfolding predicament directly co-relates to deprivation of social and economic needs being unmet and neglected by the state. The rise of elites/’middle class’ within the tribal society, emerging gender rights and issues on land and other encompassing contemporary issues are adding in to new dynamics, which needs to be considered in unravelling the debates on land.

Endnotes

¹ Tribe is synonymously with Indigenous people in this paper.

² Angamben (2009: 39-54), reads contemporary as the prism of seeing the shadows of the light, to see the obscurity. Those who are truly contemporary, or truly belong to their time are those who neither perfectly coincide with it nor adjust themselves to meet its demand. It is the “invisibility of light/darkness of the present cast its shadow on the past, so that the past, touched by this shadow, acquired the ability to respond the darkness of the now”.

³ In ‘post-colonial’ India the termed ‘Scheduled Tribe’⁴ was adopted and became a

standardised concept as a politico-administrative usage across regions.

⁵ *Lallup* system was a feudal service rendered by the subjects to Meitei Monarch. Hill dwellers particularly Rongmei Nagas (also known as Kabuis) were forced to render service as soldiers and labourers during wartime and as workers in peacetime.

⁶ In British version of *Lallup*, tribals were colonially recruited to work as labourer and coolie workers in the 2nd world war, also popularly known as France labor Corps 1917.

⁷ I have used the termed unallied tribes as those tribes who are neither claimed as Nagas nor kukis. They include Kom, Hmar, Paite and few others. The political assertion of these tribes as a distinct tribal group (entity), disincline to any of the wo major ethnic group (the Nagas and the Kukis); emerged more evidently in the recent intellectual and political discourse to uphold their own tribe/community or identity as fundamental to social, cultural and political expression without being bullied by others.

⁸ See, Manipur Forest rules, 1971 & Manipur Wildlife Protection Act 1974.

⁹ Although ‘unclassified forest’ is identified as forest areas owned by govt., individuals and community”. However, in hill areas of Manipur there is no government ‘khas land’. Land is owned by the community and individuals.

¹⁰ Some of the few noted few rich mineral zone in Ukhrul had been identified and (signed MOU on several areas) by state government are: ‘Lime Stone’ in Hungpung, Khangkhui, New Paoyi, part of Phungyar; ‘Chromite’ at Phangrei, Shirui, Lunggar, Chingai, KalhangKhunou, Poi, Halang, Pushing, Shingcha, Gamnom, Yantem, Hangkao, Apong, Ningthi, Pihang, Chattrick Khunou, Nambisha and Kangpat in Ukhrul District (Indian Bureau of Mine 2013); ‘Nickel’ with 74,000 ppm in between Gamnom and Ningthi, Pushing village and in area between Yentem to Hangkau, Apong; and ‘Copper’ in Nampisha and yentem village (Department of Commerce, Trade and Industries, Govt. of Manipur). See in the official website – <https://dcimanipur.gov.in/index.html>

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